

Classification Vectors as a Tool for Modelling Human Speech Perception

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Abstract. Humans perceive speech through the lens of their native phonemic categories, which fundamentally shape both the identification and discrimination of speech sounds. This connection between how we identify and discriminate phonemes is widely recognised as the phenomenon of Categorical Perception. We present two studies that quantitatively explore the role of categorical perception in human speech perception, focusing on how native phonemic categories influence the identification and discrimination of speech sounds when comparing an approach which operationalises categorical perception compared to one that does not. In Study 1, we apply classification vectors to model English-listener identification experiments, using Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) and other input representations such as wav2vec 2.0 and DeepSpeech2. Study 2 extends this approach to English-listener discrimination experiments. Our findings indicate that computational models, particularly those using wav2vec 2.0, offer more precise simulations of human speech perception surpassing acoustic-only models. By demonstrating that these classification vectors can effectively model both identification and discrimination tasks, this research provides a quantitative framework that solidifies the importance of categorical perception in human speech perception.

Keywords: computational linguistics; categorical perception; computational modelling

1 Introduction

Babies acquire their native phonemic categories roughly by the time they turn 12 months old (Polka, 1996; Werker & Tees, 1984). From this point, we keep these categories through and past adulthood. We use these categories every time we perceive speech sounds, as they guide and heavily influence our identification (‘classification’) of sounds (Liberman et al., 1957). Ultimately, we perceive all speech sounds in terms of these native phonemic categories, even if the sounds are not present in our native language. Moreover, our ease in classifying sounds is directly related to how easy it is to tell them apart (‘discrimination’). This relationship between identification and discrimination is fleshed out in the notion of categorical perception, which is described in more detail below.

The *Perceptual Assimilation Model* (PAM) is a prominent model of human speech perception in the literature (Best, 1995). It states that non-native speech perception is dependent on the way a listener classifies a non-native sound with respect to their native categories. Crucially, PAM allows this classification to be indeterminate, meaning that the non-native sound is not perceived as similar enough to any native sound, and thus does not get classified as any. However, a limitation of PAM is that it is a qualitative model, and thus is difficult to validate with human data.

To address the limitations of PAM while building on its foundation, Levy (2009) proposes the *overlap score*, a quantitative metric for predicting human speech perception which describes how similar a given pair of phones are. The overlap score has been found to have a strong correlation with human discrimination task results, ultimately supporting the findings of PAM.

While the literature on the effects of categorical perception on human speech perception is vast, few studies have evaluated categorical perception using an explicit computational model applied to the stimuli human listeners heard in an experiment. Thus, this current paper seeks to address this gap in the literature. Explicitly, we study the effect categorical perception has on human speech perception

through two computational modelling studies. In Study 1, we examine the question using classification vectors to model English-listener identification experiments, and, in Study 2, we use classification vectors to model English-listener discrimination experiments. We seek to determine whether predicted categorical perception explains listeners' behaviour better than a model that only makes use of the acoustic signal, without categories.

1.1 Identification Tasks

A *phoneme identification task* is a task where participants have a sound played for them, and then are asked to identify which sound they heard out of a set of options, usually in the form of sample words from their native language.

A simple example of this is of the form where an English speaker would have a sound played for them of the sound /pæf/, and would be asked, 'Which of the English vowel sounds is the central vowel of this syllable most similar to?' Participants would see the following list of response words, followed by their respective IPA forms: 'kit' /kɪt/, 'dress' /dres/, 'trap' /træp/, 'stop' /stɒp/, 'strut' /strʌt/, 'look' /lʊk/, 'fleece' /flis/, 'goat' /gəʊt/, 'tape' /teɪp/, and 'loop' /lu:p/. More likely than not, the English native speaker would respond 'trap'.

1.2 Discrimination Tasks

An *ABX phoneme discrimination task* is a task where participants have three sound files played for them, call them A, B, and X, the participants listen to them and respond with which sound they felt was closer to X: A or B.

An example of such a task could involve playing three sound files for an English speaker participant; A: 'rush', B: 'book' and X: 'bush'. When asked which sound is more similar to X; A or B, more likely than not, the participant will respond B. In an example like this, B is the 'correct' answer, while A is 'incorrect'. In many cases, the stimuli are not real words, though these are used for ease of explanation. Results from discrimination tasks serve to tell us how easily participants find it to discriminate between the sounds A and B.

1.3 Experimental Data (Millet et al., 2021)

In both Study 1 and Study 2, we use the data from Millet et al. (2021). Their study produced experimental results from English and French speakers that participated in a phoneme identification task. The dataset includes CVC sound file stimuli of vowels from seven languages: 'twelve Brazilian Portuguese vowels ([ĩ], [i], [e], [ɛ], [ẽ], [ũ], [u], [ẽ], [õ], [o], [a], [ɔ]), seven standard German vowels ([e], [i], [ɛ], [a], [o], [ɔ], [a:]), eight Bavarian-accented (Münich) German vowels ([i:], [ɪ], [y], [ʊ], [ø], [y:], [u:], [a:]), five Turkish vowels ([i], [y], [u], [ʉ], [œ]), six Estonian vowels ([i:], [ø:], [y:], [ɣ:], [æ:], [a:]), thirteen French vowels ([i], [ɛ], [e], [œ], [a], [ɔ̃], [y], [ø], [o], [u], [ɔ], [ɛ̃], [ã]), and ten English vowels ([i], [ɪ], [ɛ], [eɪ], [u], [ʊ], [ʌ], [oʊ], [æ], [ɑ])' (Millet et al., 2021, p. 662). English and French participants each saw their response options in their own native languages. For our current paper, we focus on modeling the English results.

We begin by focusing on the response data from the study, in particular, that of the English listeners. Looking at this data, we see, on average, how the participants responded to a specific stimulus. We begin with the example of [ɣ:] from Estonian. Figure 1 shows how English speakers, on average, identified [ɣ:] with respect to their native phonemes. We can see that, on average, English speakers

identified [ɤ:] as [u] most often, then [ʊ] as the second most common response, with a small proportion as [oʊ]. The other options generally received no responses.

Figure 1: Average English-listener participant's assimilation profile for Estonian [ɤ:] vowel.

For the remainder of this paper, this type of figure, showing how a speaker group identifies a specific sound, p, with respect to their native phonemes, will be referred to as the *assimilation profile* of p.

It has been documented in the literature that speakers of the same native language background tend to pattern their responses to such tasks in the same ways (Abramson & Lisker, 1970). We can see this by comparing three assimilation profiles from the data, namely Estonian [ɤ:], French [o], and Brazilian Portuguese [u]. We see from Figure 2 that on average, English speakers identify these vowels in the same way; that is, they have similar assimilation profiles. In contrast, on the right-hand side of Figure 2, we see that French speakers do not share this behaviour, as their assimilation profiles for these vowels are not the same when compared with each other.

Figure 2: Average assimilation profiles for Estonian [ɤ:], French [o], and Brazilian Portuguese [u], for both English-listener participants and French-listener participants.

In Study 1, we model the data shown in Figure 3, which shows the identification data for the English participants for all of the stimuli from Millet et al. (2021). We will do this by simulating the process of phoneme classification using a classifier.

Figure 3: Average assimilation profiles for English-listener participants, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset.

1.4 Articulation Index Corpus (Wright, 2005)

This dataset contains sound files in CV and VC syllables which contrast all English vowels. For the purpose of this study, the /ɔ/ vowel was omitted to match Millet et al. (2021). They excluded this vowel from their experiment because many of their American English-speaking participants merge this vowel with /a/.

1.5 Classification Vectoriser

For the purposes of this study, we will be constructing a *classification vectoriser*, which follows the principles of *k-Nearest Neighbours* (kNN). kNN is a *classifier*, an automated system that produces a prediction for what category something is. Classifiers are built using reference data for which category labels are known, and then can be applied to future new examples, never before seen by the classifier, to assign them category labels.

kNN is a classifier which begins with reference data, which is represented as points in Cartesian space, and has a class label associated with each data point. Thus, data is first converted from its original form into representations in Cartesian space. A method which is used to convert the data in this way will be referred to as its *input representation*, for which there are a variety of different options used and being developed.

Then, for each new data point for which the class label is not known, kNN follows this series of steps:

- (1) Compute the distance between the new point and *every* point in the reference set.
- (2) Find the *k*-nearest neighbours to the new point, using some way to compute and compare distance (for example, Euclidean distance or cosine distance). Here, *k* is a constant number. We will discuss the specific *k* value chosen in a later section. The *k*-nearest neighbours are simply the *k* closest points.

- (3) Tally the class labels for each of the k -nearest neighbours.
- (4) Finally, output the class label associated with the most tallies from the k -nearest neighbours.

To modify this procedure to make a classification vectoriser, we change step (4). Instead, we use the tallies to construct a predicted assimilation profile of that new point. To do this, we simply convert the tallies to proportions, which represent what proportion of the k -nearest neighbours are of a given phone label. For the purposes of this study, we will refer to assimilation profiles of new points which are outputs of this classifier as *classification vectors*, keeping ‘assimilation profile’ reserved only for referring to human results.

1.6 Optimal k -Value

A common heuristic for selecting the value of k in k -Nearest Neighbors is N , where N is the number of points in the reference set (Cover & Hart, 1967; Cover, 1968). This is a heuristic that is often paired with cross-validation of different k -values. In our case, different k -values made little to no difference, thus, we adhere to this, choosing $k = N$ as our final value.

1.7 Categorical Perception

As previously mentioned, humans perceive sounds in terms of their native phonemic categories, but in more recent literature, it has been suggested that we use the entire assimilation profiles of sounds to predict what phoneme they are (Levy, 2009; Gwilliams et al., 2018). This connection between how we identify sounds (their assimilation profiles) and how we discriminate between them (telling them apart) is widely known as the phenomena of Categorical Perception, which generally states that the closer two sounds are in identification, the more difficult it will be to discriminate between them, and vice versa. The behaviour of the area in between, where sounds are somewhat similar to each other in identification, is much less agreed upon in the literature. Thus, to model the effects of categorical perception, we must first model human identification experiments.

2 Study 1: Using Classification Vectors to Model Human Identification Experiments

We use a classification vectoriser of the form described above to classify English vowels. However, since modelling identification data using classification vectors has not been investigated in the literature, it is unclear what method for converting sounds into points in Cartesian space would yield the best prediction of human behaviour, if any. This leads us to the key questions we discuss in this first study: (1) Can we simulate the process of phoneme identification using a classifier? (2) Which input representation simulates the process of phoneme identification best?

To answer the first question, we look for an intuitive input representation. While we could be tempted to use formants since they are simple to convert to two-dimensional points in space, formants lack information encoding nasality, which is an important contrast in many of the world languages (and in the data from Millet et al., 2021, as well). Thus, we will choose perhaps the next intuition: some form of a spectrogram.

In considering how to represent speech audio for this purpose, we opted for the *Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficient* (MFCC) over the raw Mel filter bank representations (Mermelstein, 1976). While

MF representations capture the energy present in the Mel-scale frequency bands, MFCCs go a step further by applying a discrete cosine transform to these filter bank energies. This process decorrelates the features and emphasises the most important coefficients.

For our analysis, we use the first 13 MFCC coefficients for each sound file in the dataset, which are computed using Librosa (McFee et al., 2015). Additionally, we trimmed each sound file to only compare 65ms of the vowel portion of the CVC syllable, averaging the MFCC representations across the time dimension to end with a single 13-dimensional vector for each sound file.

To model the phoneme classification process of an English speaker, we trained a classification vectoriser (of the form described above) on the Articulation Index Corpus. For the purpose of this study, only one representative from the *caught-cot* vowel merger was kept, keeping the data balanced and matching the data from Millet et al. (2021). Moreover, similar to the process described above, the stimuli from the Articulation Index Corpus were transformed into MFCC representations, keeping 65ms of the vowel, and averaging across the time dimension to get a single 13-dimensional vector for each sound file.

To simulate the process of phoneme classification, the trained vectoriser provided classification vectors for each sound from Millet et al. (2021) data. Then, classification vectors representing the same vowels were averaged together to result in the average classification vectors for each vowel. These results are summarised in Figure 4. From the results, we see that the MFCC input representation generally follows the same pattern observed from the English listener data, but generally overpredicts the possible category responses of each vowel, and thus underpredicts how sure English listener participants are when answering. Thus, the answer to the first question is generally yes, with room for improvement.

Figure 4: Average classification vectors produced from an English trained classification vectoriser, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset, computed using MFCC input representations.

To answer the second question, we compare the MFCC results with a different input representation, namely, *wav2vec 2.0* (Baevski et al., 2020). *Wav2vec 2.0* is different from MFCCs as it is a trained neural network model, rather than simply a series of computations done on a sound file. Moreover, *wav2vec 2.0* is widely used today in the literature instead of MFCCs, as it is often seen to self-discover the underlying phonemic structure of a language without explicitly being trained to do so. The *wav2vec 2.0* model we use is pretrained in English, and we take our representations from layer 4 of the context network (for details on this architecture, see Baevski et al., 2020). Using the same method of averaging across the time dimension as discussed in the above section on MFCCs, we obtain a 768-dimensional vector for each sound file in the datasets used.

Figure 5 shows that, when simulating the process of phoneme identification using the *wav2vec 2.0* representations, *wav2vec 2.0* performs much closer to the English results compared to MFCCs. It

is more certain of the classifications, while also answering predominantly the same way English-listener participants did.

Figure 5: Average classification vectors produced from an English trained classification vectoriser, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset, computed using wav2vec 2.0 input representations.

This process was repeated with another input representation, particularly DeepSpeech2 (Amodei et al., 2015). This representation, like wav2vec 2.0, is a model, but unlike wav2vec 2.0, it is a supervised model — meaning that in its training, it was provided with labelled data, rather than unlabelled data like wav2vec 2.0. The vectors produced by this model live in 1024-dimensional space. From Figure 6, we see that DeepSpeech2 gave similar results to wav2vec 2.0. We can quantify these differences between classification vectors from each input representation and the responses given by English-listener participants as a 70% similarity between the MFCC results and the English results, an 81% similarity for wav2vec 2.0, and a with 78% similarity DeepSpeech2. Here, similarity is measured as the Pearson correlation between the assimilation profiles and the classification vectors of a given vowel.

Figure 6: Average classification vectors produced from an English trained classification vectoriser, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset, computed using DeepSpeech2 input representations.

Thus, to the second question of which input representation currently simulates the process of English phoneme identification best, our answer is wav2vec 2.0.

3 Study 2: Using Classification Vectors to Model Human Discrimination Experiments

One method to model discrimination experiments is through distances. Specifically, each sound file is converted into a point in Cartesian space using some input representation, like the ones described in the previous study. From there, for each trial in an ABX task, the distances between A and X and between B and X are compared. The difference (‘delta’) between A and X and between B and X is recorded for each trial. If this method of comparing distances is a good model of English listener responses, these deltas and whether English listeners answer correctly should be well correlated.

The process of converting sound files to points in Cartesian space and measuring distances has been investigated in the literature (Millet & Dunbar, 2022). However, using purely how similar/dissimilar input representations of a sound are does not take phonemic categories into account. I operationalise the idea of phonemic categories through classification vectors. In this study, we answer the question of whether we can simulate the process of phoneme discrimination better using classification vectors (as computed in the previous study).

Thus, in this study, we begin by converting the sound files from Millet et al. (2021) and the Articulation Index Corpus to various input representations: MFCC, wav2vec 2.0, and DeepSpeech2. We use a classification vectoriser (of the form described above) trained on the Articulation Index Corpus to produce classification vectors for each of the stimuli in the Millet et al. (2021) dataset. Then, we will simulate an ABX phoneme discrimination task by comparing the distances between the classification vectors of A and X, and of B and X. We will measure how well this method works compared to the method of computing deltas directly from the input representations of A, B, and X, by the correlations between the deltas and whether English listeners got the correct answer.

Table 1: *Pearson correlation between deltas of input representations (MFCC, wav2vec 2.0, DeepSpeech2) in an ABX trial and whether English-listener participants answered correctly in the same trial, for both conditions: Directly from input representations and using classification vector*

Input Representation	Condition	
	Directly from Input Representation	Classification Vectors
MFCC	0.517	0.649
Wav2vec 2.0	0.572	0.680
DeepSpeech2	0.672	0.714

As we can see from Table 1, across all input representations, the method of computing deltas from classification vectors outperforms the method of computing deltas directly from input representations in a statistically significant way ($p < 0.05$). Thus, we can conclude that incorporating the notion of assimilation profiles when modelling English-listener discrimination behaviour is a better representation of English-listeners’ behaviour than simply using the raw representations of the sounds.

4 Summary and Discussions

In summary, in Study 1, we demonstrate that kNN classification gives similar results to English-listener phone identification experiments, with wav2vec 2.0 doing much better than MFCC. In Study 2, we show that using classification vectors improves models of English-listener discrimination tasks, supporting the idea of categorical perception.

The assimilation profiles using a simulated model predict human behaviour remarkably well. This is surprising given that the architecture of the classification vectoriser we use is very simple. Furthermore, the representations derived from machine learned models of speech are far better than

spectral representations, presumably because they emphasise linguistically relevant information. This is true even for wav2vec 2.0, in spite of the fact that it is not trained with explicit phoneme labels.

Moreover, our measure of similarity between the classification vectors (δ) is an excellent predictor of discriminability in English-speaking listeners, much better than comparing the numerical representations directly. Not only does this strongly support the idea of categorical perception, but it also supports the proposal of Levy (2009) that the overlap in assimilation profiles forms the link between identification and discrimination in human listeners.

A limitation of this study is that we have studied only English-speaking listeners. In future work, we will extend the study to the French-speaking listeners studied by Millet et al. (2021).

5 References

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